

Climate and Hydrological Variability Trends in the Mahakali River Basin

Ravindra Pratap Singh* Pooja Singh** Bhupendra Kumar Mishra***

ABSTRACT

The Mahakali River basin is a transboundary river between India and Nepal that exhibits complex fluvial geomorphology and climatic variability. This study applies theoretical concepts to analyze river behaviour and its response to climate, tectonics, human interventions, and mining practices. The study finds that the river runoff is mainly driven by the monsoon, but is also influenced by snowmelt during winter. The basin has witnessed anomalous trends in temperature, precipitation, and runoff, indicating a higher frequency of extreme events. The study also assesses the morphometric indices of the basin, which reveal the susceptibility of different sub-basins to erosion and slope failures. The study identifies the Lower Kali Basin as the most vulnerable to tectonic and anthropogenic impacts, especially due to the proposed multipurpose dam and the ongoing road development projects. The study also evaluates the environmental and social impacts of mining in the basin, which can cause soil erosion, sinkholes, biodiversity loss, water contamination, carbon emissions, social conflicts, and cultural degradation. The study also highlights the challenges of developing hydrological models in the Himalayan region due to the lack of in-situ data and the uncertainty of satellite-based products. The study provides a holistic view of the landscape morphology and the processes involved in sculpting it, and also a window to be alert during the monsoon season along this Lesser Himalayan valley. The study recommends environmentally sustainable and socially responsible mining practices that respect the rights and interests of the local communities and the transboundary cooperation between India and Nepal.

Key words: Mahakali River basin, morphometric controls, climate inconsistency, hydrological variabilities

INTRODUCTION

Climate variability and hydrological trends are important topics for understanding the impacts of climate change on water resources and ecosystems. Understanding the causes and consequences of these phenomena is essential for developing adaptation and mitigation strategies to cope with the current and future challenges of water security and sustainability. However, there are many uncertainties and complexities involved in studying the interactions between climate variability, hydrological trends, and human activities, especially at the regional and local scales. This paper aims to provide a general introduction to the topic of climate variability and hydrological trends, with a focus on the Mahakali river basin. The river is also known as the Sarda or Kali River, which is a transboundary river that originates from the high Himalayas and flows through Nepal and India. It is a mountain-fed catchment of

the Ghagra sub-basin in the Ganga Flow System. The river merges with the Ghaghra River near Gaurahee (Lakhimpur Kheri district of Uttar Pradesh) after flowing through the *Terai plains* originating from the Trans Himalayan region. The river demarcates the international administrative boundary of Nepal (far Western regions) and India (Uttarakhand Kumaon division).

The aim of this research paper is to analyze the long-term (1981-2020) changes in the climate of the Mahakali River basin, which is located in a region that has experienced anomalous patterns of heavy rainfall and rising near surface temperature (up to 0.6°C in the last century). These changes have created a climatic crisis in recent decades (IPCC, 2001) that is evident in both global and basin-scale climate data. The paper also seeks to understand the relationship between the morphological and climatic features of the basin in the same period, with a special focus on the higher altitude regions that are more vulnerable to climatic variations.

STUDY AREA

The Mahakali river basin covers an area of more than 15,000

*Department of Earth and Planetary Sciences, University of Allahabad, Prayagraj, Uttar Pradesh, India-211002.

**Department of Computer Application, Maharaja Surajmal Institute, Janakpuri, New Delhi-110058.

***Department of Mining, AKS University, Satna, Madhya Pradesh, India-485001

Corresponding Author: rpsinghsaran@allduniv.ac.in

km², of which almost 65% lies in India and the rest in Nepal (Pandey et al. 2019). The climate of the Mahakali River basin is influenced by the monsoon system, which brings about 70% of the annual precipitation from the south-western monsoonal precipitation (Panda et al. 2013). The complex and dynamic system of the Mahakali River basin marks it as a hotspot of transboundary cooperation and conflict, as the river is shared by two countries, which have different interests and perspectives on its management and development. The basin faces multiple challenges and opportunities, such as climate change, water scarcity, hydropower generation, biodiversity conservation, disaster risk reduction, and socio-economic development, which require scientific evidence and policy dialogue to address them effectively. The basin covers four districts of far Western Nepal (Baitadi, Dadeldhura, Kanchanpur and Darchula districts) and six districts of Indian Kumaon Himalayas (Pithoragarh, Champawat, Bageshwar, Almora and Udham Singh Nagar). The Lipulekh and Limpayadhura pass also lies in the Mahakali River Basin and marks an important border with Tibet (Trust, 2017). The river originates near Kalapani (at an altitude of 3,600 m), Pithoragarh district from the Uttarakhand Himalayas and flows through narrow gorges passing through Garbyang, Tawaghat and Dharchula in the upper reaches, which becomes wider after Brahmadev Mandi near Tanakpur at the entry point of Terai Plains (Midha and Mathur 2013). The Darma, Gauri Ganga, Chimilia, Sarju, Lodhiya and Ramgun rivers join the trunk river at Tawaghat, Jaulgibi, Gurans Himal, Jhulaghat and Jogbudha Valley respectively.

The basin can be divided into four physiographic divisions, Higher Himalayan Zone, Lesser Himalayan Zone, Shivalik and Terai plains. The basin also experiences considerable spatial and temporal variability in rainfall and temperature, due to the complex topography and elevation gradient. The basin has a range of climatic zones, from alpine to subtropical, and hosts various types of ecosystems, such as forests, grasslands, wetlands, and agricultural lands. The climate of the basin is also projected to change in the future, with possible impacts on the water resources, biodiversity, and livelihoods of the people. The Higher Himalayan region of the basin is mostly snow-covered with steep barren slopes, while the Lesser Himalayan gentle slopes have dense vegetation cover over, which is more or less continuous in the Siwalik region. The *Tarai Plains* are composed of Himalayan sediments and are known for their dense Sal Forests and grassland around seasonal swamps. The dendritic drainage pattern at the upper reaches of the basin mark deep eroded Tethys

Sedimentary Sequence (TSS) and the Higher Himalayan Crystallines (HHC). Linear drainage patterns at places along the Lesser Himalayan metasedimentary (LHS), the Siwaliks, and the alluvial plains show erosional incompetence along the region. The molassic sediments derived from the erosion of the Himalayas are known as the Muree and Siwalik formations. These formations are internally folded and imbricated. The sub-Himalaya is thrust along the Main Frontal thrust (MFT) over the Quaternary alluvium deposit which signifies its active movement of Himalaya. This area has stream bed deposits and alluvium of Holocene age. Siwalik group consists of sandstone, shale and claystone of Pliocene and Pleistocene age. Muree formations have sandstone, shale and claystone (Manandhar et al., 2012).

Gori Ganga and Dhauri Ganga valleys show a variety of rocks like gneisses, migmatites, psammitic, quartzite, marble, mica schist and amphibolite exists. A north-north easterly dipping major tectonic plane in Kumaon region termed as Main Central Thrust is the northern tectonic limit of sedimentation of the Garhwal group with the Central Crystalline (Trust, 2017). Saryu and Ladhiya valley have sequence of Garhwal group comprises Shale, Slate, Phyllite, quartzite, dolomite, limestone, magnesite, occasional calc slate and metavolcanics (Trust, 2017). The trunk river crosses through the Trans Himadri Fault (THF; likeness to the South Tibet Separation System; STDS), which isolates the limit between TSS and schistose rocks of Buddi Formation, among Garbayang and Buddi. The stream also cut across the Main Central Thrust (MCT) close Pangla and moves through the synclinal collapsed Chhiplakot nappe among Pangla and Dharchula, which speaks to a subsequent enormous (after Almora nappe) thrust sheet, which is presently disengaged from its root zone (Talukdar et al., 2020).

The northern and southern limit of Chhiplakot nappe is set apart by North Chhiplakot Thrust (NCT) and South Chhiplakot Thrust (SCT), individually. Between Dharchula and Joljibi, the Kali River courses through the metasedimentary of the Inner Lesser Himalaya (Valdiya, 1980) and streams over the Berinag Thrust (BT) zone. In the focal part, the waterway streams through the synclinally collapsed, low to medium grade transformative rocks of the Almora Nappe (AN), laying on the Lesser Himalayan metasedimentary succession. The northern limit of AN is characterized as North Almora Thrust (NAT), and the southern limit is known as South Almora Thrust (SAT; Valdiya, 1980). The nappe zone includes the Saryu

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Formation of the Almora Group, record and quartzite of the Rautgara Formation, quartzite with meta basics of the Berinag Formation, and Deoban limestone (Valdiya, 1980). Towards the lower comes to, the waterway streams over the 2 km wide zone of Ramgarh Thrust that comprises of Paleoproterozoic rocks of the Lesser Himalaya groupings. Further downstream, the Kali Waterway streams over the Fundamental Limit Thrust (MBT) zone. The steeply inclined thrust plane has brought Lesser Himalayan rocks upon

the Cenozoic sedimentary territory of the External Himalaya. Nonetheless, towards the Himalayan front, the waterway streams over the Himalayan Frontal Thrust (HFT), which characterizes the southern limit of the Himalaya against the Indo Gangetic Fields of Quaternary age. The alluvial fans (Bastiya Fan) at the mouths of settled in streams getting through the raised slope front are elevated and disfigured into pressure edges and dejections adjoining the Himalayan Frontal Fault (HFF) (Valdiya, 1982)

Figure 1: Geology of the the Upper Mahakali Basin

There are several contrasts can be observed in terms of geology and climate and thus in geomorphology in plane, Terai and Himalayan region. In hill ranges, Synclinal valleys play an important role, it forms due to linear stream erosion. Valley floors contain fluvioglacial outwash materials and often form erosional terraces due to entrenchment of

longitudinal streams. By drainage system, the mountain ranges show a deep dissection which shows a dendritic pattern. (Trust, 2017). The silt consists of Sharda River flows downward from the Himalaya and Siwaliks into the flat Gangetic plain of Uttar Pradesh which creates a landscape known as Terai. The region is known for dense

Sal Forest, wet tall grasslands and shallow seasonal swamps. Geological structure consists of old and new alluvium. The new alluvium gets renewed every year by fresh deposits brought down by active streams. Old alluvium is found away from river courses on uplands of the plain.

Plain zone is the place where deposition process forms multiple paths with shallow beds, enabling massive floods as monsoon-swollen rivers overflow their low banks and shift channels. Many areas show erosion in the form of gullies which is highly fertile soil i.e., red, Terai and alluvial soil.

In a major part of the mountainous region which is known as Terai region, subtropical climate prevails and average temperature of this zone is 25 degrees. Rainfall varies from 1200mm to 3000mm per annum with rare cloudbursts. In monsoonal months, from June to September runoff increases which causes flooding in the area. Rivers coming from mountainous regions provide water for the settlement near the Shivalik hills and Churia hills. This region is also termed as the granary of the nation in the Nepal region. In the plain region, the weather is very hot in summer and very cold in winter having high precipitation by making this area suitable for farming with highly fertile soil. In the month from mid-April to the end of May, hot wind known as Loo prevails. The basin also experiences frequent cloudburst events too, as 90% of rainfall occurs in the monsoonal period where rainfall intensity of 350mm for consecutive 48 hours is considered as high intensity rainfall. Rainfall exceeding 70mm/hour is considered as cloudburst rainfall and it can disrupt slope and channel equilibrium at local and regional levels. (Adhikari, 2013)

METHODOLOGY

The research work incorporates the data from climate and other data available in public domain. The major resource used for the study is ECMWF (European Community for Medium-Reach Climate Estimates). The ECMWF teamed up with a few organizations to foster ERA5, a re-investigation of meteorological perceptions from January 1981 to December 2020. This dataset incorporates the environment data of a very long while related with land influencing factors. Reanalysis joins mathematical model data alongside perceptions from across the world into a total and unsurprising environment dataset. The perceptions got then can straightforwardly be utilized for future investigation of environment patterns.

The research work is mainly discussed with the topographic and the climatic datasets. The **Topographical Data** provides information about the surface elevation and its distribution to analyze the basin and/or drainage parameters, like drainage pattern, basin morphology, drainage control over the basin, etc. Whereas, the **Climatic Data** has vast directory to deliberate but only three major controlling parameters, precipitation, runoff and temperature, have been opted considering the time frame and scope of the research work.

The JAXAs Global ALOS digital elevation model (ALOS DEM) collected from the NASA Earth Data available at the public domain. The ALOS DEM is a high-resolution SAR (Synthetic Aperture Radar) data, with 32-bit pixel value are and 12.5m resolution. The basin and other basin parameters have been developed with the help of *Hydrology Tool* of Arc GIS by marking the pour point. The drainage network has been extracting from was used to calculate linear, areal and relief basin morphometric parameters. The stream network of the basin was extracted with geo-processing tool as per Strahler (1964) and Mahala (2020), i.e., where segments with no tributaries identified as a 1st order stream and when at least the two 1st order stream joins form a 2nd order stream and so on. The trunk river, Mahakali, is computed as 8th order river in the basin after merging of Gauriganga river at Jauljibi.

The climatic elements considered for the research work are **2m Temperature, Runoff and Precipitation**. The datasets of these climatic elements downloaded from the Copernicus Environment Information Store under the ERA5-Land hourly information from 1981 to present accessed on www.cds.climate.copernicus.eu. The data collected in '**netCDF format**' among available two format options with a global coverage of January 1981 to December 2020 temporal spread. The downloaded data have hourly temporal resolution, and the information acquired in 5 years interval time frames, e.g., from 1981 to 1985 and 1986 to 1990 and so on. The following climatic elements download from Copernicus (2020):

2m Temperature: Temperature of air at 2m over the surface of land, ocean or in-land waters. The data are stored in the kelvin (K). The temperature assessed in kelvin can be changed over to degrees Celsius (°C) by subtracting it from 273.15. This parameter is calculated by interpolating between the lowest model level and the earth's surface, taking account of the atmospheric conditions.

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Total Precipitation: It is collected fluid and frozen water, including precipitation and snow, that received by the earth surface. It does exclude mist, dew and precipitation that didn't landed on the surface. It is estimated in m. Accumulated liquid and frozen water, including rain and snow that falls to the Earth's surface. It is the sum of large-scale precipitation and convective precipitation. Precipitation variables do not include fog, dew or the precipitation that evaporates in the atmosphere before it lands at the surface of the Earth. This variable is accumulated from the beginning of the forecast time to the end of the forecast step. The units of precipitation are depth in meters. It is the depth the water would have if it were spread evenly over the grid box.

deep in the soil, stays stored in the soil. Otherwise, the water drains away, either over the surface (surface runoff), or under the ground (sub-surface runoff) and the sum of these two is simply called 'runoff'. The units of runoff are depth in meters. This variable is the total amount of water accumulated from the beginning of the forecast time to the end of the forecast step. The units of runoff are depth in meters. Runoff is a measure of the availability of water in the soil, and can be used as an indicator of drought or flood.

All the mentioned climate datasets, i.e., collected is of 40 years from 1981 to 2020 and are of 24 hours of each day in NET.CDF (Experimental Format) and thereafter of form is submitted to download and access these data.

Total Runoff: Some water from rainfall, melting snow, or

Table 1: A brief about the properties of the data used for the research work (downloaded from ECMWF and Earth Data Search NASA)

Variables	Datasets	Availability	Resolution	
			Temporal	Spatial
Total Precipitation (in m)	ERA5 Land hourly data	1981 to 2020	Hourly	0.1°×0.1°
2M Temperature (in K)		1981 to 2020	Hourly	0.1°×0.1°
Total Runoff (in m)		1981 to 2020	Hourly	0.1°×0.1°
Elevation (in m)	SAR data	Recent	-	12.5m

DATA PROCESSING

The data collected from the source mentioned above has been processed on GIS and other platforms for analyses in order to come up with some sensible result or correlation. The fluvial geomorphology provides a holistic view of the landscapes morphology and the processes involved in sculpturing them. So, it serves as tool and effective approach for reading a landscape in a diversified river setting with variable roles of climate and tectonics and also the role of human interventions affecting them. It involves the application of theoretical concepts with the field-based investigations to interpret and analyze the river behavior. In this study Remote sensing and GIS analysis techniques are used to determine geological and morphometric properties of kali river basin that marks the eastern international border between the India and Nepal. A drainage basin reflects its geology with subsurface lithology and geomorphic processes that have operated over time and slope as indicated by various morphometric studies. Drainage morphometry was first initiated by Horton (1932). Several software packages available for analyzing

drainage basin parameters in raster grids of satellite images and digital elevation models (DEMs). These extensions and algorithms are used for extraction of drainage networks Morphometric analysis used to identify specific features, process zones, and component parts of 'riverscapes' from continuous data (Wheaton et.al. 2015). Also used to understand the process and organization shaping river. The relationship between drainage morphometric parameters to its underlain geology, geomorphology and hydrological characteristics is established through the work of different geologist and geomorphologist (Strahler 1952; Chorley et al. 1985). Drainage morphometric parameters are important indicator to understand the hydrological and morphological characteristics of any region. The different morphometric characteristics like linear parameters (stream order, stream number, bifurcation ratio, strength length, mean stream length), areal or basin parameters (circularity ratio, elongation ratio, drainage density, drainage frequency) and relief parameters (dissection index, ruggedness index) are important for any river basin management (Adhikari, 2020). Drainage morphometric parameters are important indicator to understand the hydrological and morphological

characteristics of any region (Burbank & Anderson, 2001; Delcaillau, Carozza, & Laville, 2006). Increasing availability of Digital Elevation Models (DEM) and geographic information system (GIS) software has helped in identifying the large-scale characterization of landscapes in response to tectonic activity (Reshmi et.al.2017). To understand the river's form, their patterns in their organization, fluvial geomorphologists have mapped the rivers and made inferences and interpretations about the processes producing and shaping of those form. These maps of the river work as raw data to describing and quantifying the rivers. The morphometric analyses and field mapping present a critical template for a range of toolkits for integrative river science (Wheaton et al., 2015). This morphometric analysis ultimately used to understand the process and organization shaping river. Geomorphologic maps provide a platform to interpret and quantify process relationships and their controls, to evaluate river change and adjustment potential, and to assess evolutionary trajectories (Wheaton et al., 2015). In recent decades, recurrent periods of intense flooding in the Sharda River and unpredictable changes in its channel morphology have caused huge losses to the valuable biodiversity of the forest-wetland-grass-land complex and to human property (Midha et.al. 2013).

The research work incorporates results of the basic morphometric parameters for the tectonic assessment of the area, i.e., basin perimeter, basin area, minimum height, maximum height, basin length, number of stream order, length of stream order, mean stream length, stream length ratio, bifurcation ratio, mean bifurcation ratio, drainage density, stream frequency, ruggedness number, length of overland flow, basin relief, relief ratio, relative relief, texture ratio, form factor, circulatory ratio, elongation ratio, time of concentration has been calculated to study the morphology and to check the susceptibility of Mahakali basin as per methods suggested by Horton (1932 and 1945), Schumm (1956 and 1963), Strahler (1964), Ozdemir and Bird (2009) and Hardely and Schumm (1961).

Climatic data sets downloaded in the NETCDF format processed to bring it in Text format. This led to Grid analysis and Display System. Climate Data Operator used command for the processing of climate data using a set of commands. Finally, the output file of yearmean and ymonmean file is converted into graphical form by using GrADS software. After taking the data into excel, we add this XY data of climatic parameters on ArcGIS software and then exporting it as a layer file and thereafter

interpolating the data with the shape file of our basin using IDW tool, we get all the three climatic parameters in map form to analyze the variation within a year and within a month of all 40 years.

RESULTS

The study reveal that remotely sensed data (ASTER-DEM) and GIS based approaches in evaluation of drainage morphometric parameters and their influences on landforms. The drainage pattern of the study area is demarcated by., trellis, dendritic, and radial to dendritic patterns, the highest order is seventh order. The drainage (<1) density reveals that the soil of the area is having moderate to coarse texture with permeable in nature. The bifurcation ratio indicates that some region drainage patterns are structurally and lithological controlled and some areas are not. The relative ratio and basin relief indicates high basin relief, high gravity of water flow, and erosion rate. The overall shape of basin is elongated to semicircular in shape interpreted on the basis of form factor, elongation ratio and circulatory ratio.

The area is studied with the help of linear, areal and relief morphometric parameters. The parameters discussed in the methodology have been calculated for each of four sub-basins. The area has streams up to 8th order with moderate stream frequency (0.3 meter). The results show low drainage density in the western (Upper and Lower Kali River) catchments to moderately high drainage density in the eastern region. The relief parameters have low values for eastern catchments and high in the western catchments. The elongation ration is highest for the lower Kali River Basin. Low form factor of the basin (0.30 to 0.45) indicating high susceptibility to erosion. Very low values of time of concentration indicating controls of relief paraments over the region. The Gauriganga catchment is covering largest area while lower Kali River catchment is smallest. Upper Kali catchment is covering lesser area than Dhauliganga catchment but higher in length.

The plotted climate element data of 40 years (1981 to 2020) with five-year intervals represents the dominant factor governing the basin provides us the prevailing condition over the basins for prolonged period of time. The analysis is made on the basis of average annual spatial pattern and average monthly spatial pattern of a parameter along the basin. The anomaly maps also have been prepared to check the recent changes in the spatial pattern as compare to the oldest available data.

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Figure 2: Drainage map of the basin

The precipitation over the basin has a usual pattern with less rainfall in the southern planes (i.e., *Tarai* area after

Tanakpur) and less snow fall in the northern most mountains (i.e., north of Higher Himalayas). The Panchewar and Darma valleys are receiving high rainfall in the basin (Figure 3). The anomaly map (Figure 6c and 7c) of the area shows a declining pattern of precipitation along Darma valley and the Nepal Lesser Himalayan region around Darchula district. Whereas, the Higher Himalayan mountains and the Pancheshwar valley shows an increase in the precipitation during 40 years.

The monthly average rainfall of the basin shows high precipitation along Darma valley during pre-monsoon and winter monsoon but along Pancheshwar valley during monsoonal precipitation. The situation led to high risk of flooding during monsoon at the lower elevations. The situation can be worsened during August, when the both the Darma and Panchewar valley gets high precipitation. The runoff along the basin has trends similar to precipitation, i.e., higher runoff values around Pancheshwar valley and in the vicinity of Lesser Himalayan mountains. The runoff values are decreasing southward and become almost constant after foothills. The runoff anomaly map of the basin shows an increase in the runoff values north of Lesser Himalayas and decrease along the Darma valley, but interestingly the value of runoff become high near the confluence with Ghaghra river.

The scenario depicts a lesser contribution of water from the Mahakali river as compare to the major river in the recent years. Constantly increasing trend of temperature from north to south is depicted by the near surface air temperature along the basin.

May

June

July

August

September

October

November

December

Figure 3: Average Monthly Precipitation Pattern

January

February

March

April

May

June

July

August

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Figure 4: Average Monthly Runoff Pattern

Figure 5: Average Monthly Temperature Pattern

RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

The analysis of precipitation anomalies within the basin provides valuable insights into the changing rainfall patterns over the past four decades, particularly with regard to the influence of anthropogenic activities such as tourism development and their subsequent impact on regional climate dynamics. The identification of spatial distribution patterns of precipitation anomalies across the basin serves as a fundamental aspect of climate research. By employing grid-wise analysis techniques, researchers can discern localized variations in precipitation trends, which are crucial for understanding regional climate shifts and their implications.

The mention of the middle part of the basin, where significant land use changes have occurred due to tourism development in towns like Pithoragarh, Dharchula, and Munsiri, underscores the role of human activities in shaping local climate conditions. Research in this area may delve deeper into the specific mechanisms through which land use changes, such as urbanization and deforestation associated with tourism, contribute to altering temperature and precipitation patterns. The observed moderate temperature anomaly in the middle part of the basin implies potential impacts on atmospheric moisture dynamics, a key determinant of precipitation. Research exploring the complex interactions between temperature, atmospheric moisture content, and rainfall patterns in tourism-affected regions can provide valuable insights into the mechanisms driving changes in precipitation regimes.

The finding of increased rainfall intensity in the lower and upper reaches of the basin, juxtaposed with the stability in precipitation levels in the central part, highlights the spatial heterogeneity of climate change impacts within the basin. This underscores the importance of localized climate studies in accurately assessing regional climate vulnerabilities and formulating targeted adaptation strategies. Moreover, the implications of these findings extend beyond academic research to practical considerations such as water resource management and climate change adaptation. Understanding how precipitation patterns are evolving within the basin is essential for devising effective strategies to mitigate water-related risks and adapt to changing hydrological conditions, particularly in areas experiencing positive trends in rainfall. The runoff pattern map of the basin reveals a remarkable correspondence with the rainfall pattern in the last four decades. However, a striking anomaly is detected in the

middle of the basin, where the runoff remains normal despite the evident change in the landuse pattern near Pithoragarh and Dharchula. On the other hand, the runoff has increased slightly in the lower reaches of the basin, i.e., near the confluence of the river, in the last 40 years. This could be attributed to the enhanced rainfall in this region, as well as the increased surface runoff due to urbanization and deforestation. The most significant change in runoff is observed in the higher altitudes, which are predominantly glaciated or snow-covered areas. This indicates a higher degree of anthropogenic influence in the region, such as greenhouse gas emissions, black carbon deposition, and tourism activities. These factors could have accelerated the melting of glaciers and snow, resulting in increased runoff in the high-altitude streams. Interestingly, the anomaly is very low in the center of the basin, which typically receives the highest precipitation in the basin. This suggests that the natural factors, such as topography, soil, and vegetation, have a dominant role in regulating the runoff in this region. In conclusion, it can be inferred that the areas of low precipitation have experienced higher runoff in the last 40 years, while the areas of high precipitation have maintained their runoff pattern. This could be a sign of higher melting rates along the higher altitudes, which could have serious implications for the water resources and the ecosystem of the basin.

The runoff pattern map of the basin shows a strong correlation with the rainfall pattern over the past four decades. However, an anomaly is observed in the middle of the basin, where the runoff is unaffected by the apparent landuse change near Pithoragarh and Dharchula. Conversely, the runoff has slightly increased in the lower basin, near the river confluence, in the same period. This may be due to the higher rainfall in this area, as well as the enhanced surface runoff caused by urbanization and deforestation. The most notable change in runoff occurs in the higher altitudes, which are mainly glaciated or snow-covered areas. This implies a greater impact of human activities in the region, such as greenhouse gas emissions, black carbon deposition, and tourism activities. These factors may have hastened the melting of glaciers and snow, leading to increased runoff in the high-altitude streams. Interestingly, the anomaly is minimal in the center of the basin, which usually receives the highest precipitation in the basin. This indicates that the natural factors, such as topography, soil, and vegetation, play a major role in controlling the runoff in this region. Therefore, it can be concluded that the low-precipitation areas have witnessed higher runoff in the past 40 years, while the high-precipitation

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areas have preserved their runoff pattern. This could be a sign of higher melting rates along the higher altitudes, which could have severe consequences for the water resources and the ecosystem of the basin.

A significant change in the temperature is detected after the foothills or Tarai region compared to the nearby Shiwalik mountains. The average monthly temperature follows the same trend as the annual average temperature, except for the variation in values during winters. This consistent pattern of the temperature along the basin suggests that the atmospheric changes are driven by the monsoonal wind pattern along the Himalayas, rather than the surface temperature.

CONCLUSIONS

In the intricate tapestry of the country's hydrological systems, the Mahakali River basin emerges as a crucial thread, weaving together the destinies of two burgeoning nations, India and Nepal. However, this lifeline is currently navigating the turbulent waters of frequent hydrological variations, a phenomenon that has become increasingly pronounced in recent decades. Through a meticulous analysis employing various methodologies, the study has illuminated the intricate interactions among climatic, hydrological, tectonic, and geomorphic factors shaping the basin's characteristics. The study embarked on a journey to explore the ebb and flow of major climatic elements within this hydrologically sensitive river basin. The findings paint a picture of a river whose lifeblood is the monsoon, yet it also receives a generous bounty of water during the winter monsoonal period.

The observed alterations in temperature, precipitation, and runoff patterns underscore the heightened variability and uncertainty experienced within the basin. However, the winter monsoon, with its primary offering of snowfall, contributes minimally to the river's runoff, serving instead as a reservoir for the dry seasons. A closer examination of the climatic elements reveals a pattern of anomalies during the periods of 1986-90, 2001-05, and 2016-20. These irregularities signal an increase in the frequency of extreme events in the region, casting a shadow of uncertainty over the future.

This study examines the precipitation anomalies in the basin and their implications for regional climate change over the last 40 years. It analyzes the spatial distribution of precipitation anomalies using grid-wise techniques and

reveals the influence of tourism development on rainfall patterns. The study also identifies the towns in the middle part of the basin that have undergone significant land use changes due to tourism and discusses how these changes may affect temperature and precipitation. It suggests further research on the causal mechanisms linking tourism-related land use changes, such as urbanization and deforestation, with climate variability.

The study also investigates the temperature anomaly in the middle part of the basin and its possible effects on atmospheric moisture, a critical factor for precipitation. It explores the complex interplay between temperature, moisture, and rainfall in the tourism-affected areas and elucidates the processes that shape the precipitation regimes. The study compares the rainfall intensity in the lower and upper parts of the basin with the stable precipitation levels in the central part and illustrates the spatial heterogeneity of climate change impacts within the basin.

The study emphasizes the importance of localized climate studies for assessing regional climate vulnerabilities and developing tailored adaptation strategies. It also highlights the practical relevance of the findings for water resource management and climate change adaptation, as understanding the changing precipitation patterns is essential for designing effective measures to cope with water-related challenges and adapt to the altered hydrological conditions, especially in the areas with positive rainfall trends.

Furthermore, the morphometric analysis with delineation of various morphometric indices, such as basin perimeter, area, relief ratio, and drainage density, has revealed the basin's structural control and erosion potential. In light of these findings, the study proposes several recommendations to enhance the resilience and sustainability of the Mahakali River basin. Integrated flood management systems, sediment management plans, and river restoration initiatives are identified as crucial measures to mitigate hydrological risks and improve ecosystem health within the basin. The study also acknowledges the presence of limitations and gaps in the existing knowledge and data, emphasizing the need for further research to address these shortcomings. Moving forward, it is imperative for stakeholders to adopt a holistic and interdisciplinary approach in managing the Mahakali River basin. Transboundary cooperation and coordination among relevant actors are essential to ensure the effective

implementation of management strategies and the equitable distribution of resources.

The study concluded that the Mahakali River basin is a complex and dynamic system that requires a holistic and interdisciplinary approach to understand and manage its resources and challenges.

Figure 6: Precipitation pattern along the Mahakali River Basin.

- (A): Average annual precipitation pattern along the basin in 1981;
- (B): Average annual precipitation pattern along the basin in 2020;
- (C): Difference in the precipitation pattern along the basin.

CLIMATE AND HYDROLOGICAL VARIABILITY TRENDS IN THE MAHAKALI RIVER BASIN

Figure 7: Spatial distribution of Runoff over the Mahakali River Basin.

(A): Average annual runoff along the basin in 1981;
 (B): Average annual runoff along the basin in 2020;
 (C): Difference in the runoff distribution along the basin.

The runoff pattern map of the basin reveals a remarkable correspondence with the rainfall pattern in the last four decades. However, a striking anomaly is detected in the middle of the basin, where the runoff remains normal despite the evident change in the landuse pattern near Pithoragarh and Dharchula. On the other hand, the runoff has increased slightly in the lower reaches of the basin, i.e., near the confluence of the river, in the last 40 years. This could be attributed to the enhanced rainfall in this region, as well as the increased surface runoff due to urbanization and deforestation. The most significant change in runoff is observed in the higher altitudes, which are predominantly glaciated or snow-covered areas. This indicates a higher degree of anthropogenic influence in the region, such as greenhouse gas emissions, black carbon deposition, and tourism activities. These factors could have accelerated the melting of glaciers and snow, resulting in increased runoff in the high-altitude streams. Interestingly, the anomaly is very low in the center of the basin, which typically receives the highest precipitation in the basin. This suggests that the natural factors, such as topography, soil, and vegetation, have a dominant role in regulating the runoff in this region. In conclusion, it can be inferred that the areas of low precipitation have experienced higher runoff in the last 40 years, while the areas of high precipitation have maintained their runoff pattern. This could be a sign of higher melting rates along the higher altitudes, which could have serious implications for the water resources and the ecosystem of the basin.

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Address for Correspondence

Prof. Ramesh Chandra Mohapatra
Chairman, RPCIIEE-2020
Email - rameshmohapatra75@gmail.com
Contact Number - +91-9438551072

Prof. Soumya Ranjan Mallick
Convenor, RPCIIEE-2020
Email - mallicksoumyaranjan@gmail.com
Contact Number - +91-9437545820

Prof. Adiraj Behera
Organising Secretary, RPCIIEE-2020
Email - adirajbehera_fmt@gcekj.ac.in
Contact Number - +91-9440257794

Prof. Sushanta Kumar Pradhan
Organising Secretary, RPCIIEE-2020
Email - rsushantapradhan_fmt@gcekj.ac.in
Contact Number - +91-8763112083

Prof. Dayanidhi Jena
Convenor, RPCIIEE-2020
Email - dayanidhijena_fme@gcekj.ac.in
Contact Number - +91-7750865106